

Mineralogy of the Gold Deposit in Carlés - Salas, Asturias, Spain -

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Mining History

The so called Narcea River Gold Belt, in Asturias, is a set of mineralised veins stretching for 45 km between Luearca and Ibias. Many of the gold deposits had already been discovered and exploited in Roman times, with significant mining operations, as in Begega-El Valle (where a modern mine is also located, still active), Pontigo, or the so-called "Pozo Cellerico", in Ablaneda. In each of these more than one million cubic meters were extracted (Perea and Sánchez, 1995).

The Carlés gold deposit is located south of the village, in the municipality of Salas, on the left bank of the river Narcea, and was exploited in Roman times, although apparently the workings were relatively small.

On the hillside between Carlés village and the Narcea river, overlapping the modern mine workings, there are remains of several Roman surface workings, including a trench later converted into a washing channel. Also two Roman galleries, one located near the town of Carlés, could previously be seen at the head of one of the washing channels. Tool marks and carbonized timber shoring remains were found. In a lower area of the hillside, with altered mineralization, another Roman gallery with reinforcements and timber shoring was found. The ¹⁴C date of wood debris indicates use between the early first century and the middle of the third century C.E. (Villa and Fanjul, 2006).

After the abandonment of the mines by the Romans, the Carlés mineralization (and all of the Narcea River Gold Belt) were virtually forgotten, with few exceptions. In november 30 of 1625, Sebastian Martínez Espinosa and Pedro Gutierrez Pardabe were authorized to operate a copper mine that had been discovered in the area known as Cuesta del Moro, Carlés, in the Salas council (González, 1832). Toreno (1785) also mentions the existence of copper ore mixed with "azero" (steel) in Carlés. According to Paillette (1852), the Carlés mine, which he considered to be a gold mine, was almost completely buried, although there were remnants of a gallery excavated years ago by an English company, in which "coppery pyrite accompanied by white pyrite" could be seen, being probably chalcopyrite and arsenopyrite. During the modern exploitation of Carlés, a gallery of undetermined age was found. It could not be prior to the nineteenth century, given the use of boreholes

with explosives, where probably argentiferous galena was extracted (Villa and Fanjul, 2006). In the mid 1940s some efforts were made to extract arsenopyrite for the manufacture of arsenical derivatives. The most important work was known as the Bandanaso mine, and consisted of a gallery that was already buried in the 1970s.

Others works in which arsenopyrite was also extracted were known as Mina del Cura ("mine of the priest"), and consisted of two small galleries. In Peña del Mouro two more workings were located, known as the Mouro mine, and possibly copper ores were extracted there.

In the area next to the road, altered granodiorite was extracted in the 1960s, probably for construction.

In 1971 the company Gold Fields Española S.A., that was investigating the Salave gold deposit, also conducted studies on the Carlés skarn. Subsequently Boliden Minerals A.B. and Explotaciones Mineras del Cantábrico conducted geological studies and some drilling. In 1985, Anglo American Company carried out a very detailed study of the Carlés skarn, including even mineral processing tests. In 1990, it formed a joint venture company with Hullas del Coto Cortés. They investigated the area, making a gallery 1.5 km long with the entrance located next to the road, in the area known as Carlés East. In 1992 Concord Minera Asturiana joined the mining project, a subsidiary of Concord Services Inc. In 1993 the company Rio Narcea A.I.E., a subsidiary of Rio Narcea Gold Mines was formed. This company focused its work on El Valle-Boinás, although in 1996 they also conducted detailed drilling to define the mineralization and the best way to exploit it (Noble *et al.*, 2012).

Over the deposit, where the "Fortuna", "Electra" and "Magnética" concessions are located, two excavations were made, each one associated with underground workings. The biggest, designated Carlés North, is located less than 100 meters SE of the village, while the one known as Carlés East is located SE of the previous one, next to the road from Cornellana to Cangas del Narcea. The surface workings of the latter have been largely restored.

Open pit mining began in Carlés East at the end of 2000, continuing through 2002. The ore was hauled by truck to the Rio Narcea A.I.E. plant, at the El Valle-Boinás mine, for processing, with ore from both mines being mixed together. The treatment plant and the techniques used were described in detail by Mesa *et al.*, (2002).

The sterile rock was used for aggregates, and even as breakwater blocks, facilitating the continuation of mining by reducing costs. In 2002 the previous underground exploratory workings were dewatered and conditioned, and in 2003 they began to operate, until December 29, 2006, on which date the mine and the treatment plant were completely paralyzed. In Carlés North open pit operations were carried out between 2000 and 2004. Underground mining was active between 2003 and 2006, reaching more than 200 meters deep. In total, in Carlés East, 63,852 tons of ore, with 4.5 g/t gold and 0.78% copper on average, were extracted by open pit mining. And 147,254 tons of ore, with 5.06 g/t gold and 0.95% copper, were extracted in underground mining. In Carlés North, 231,000 tons of ore with 4.43 g/t gold and 0.77% copper were extracted by open pit mining. For underground mining, 296,464 tons of ore were extracted with 5.11 g/t gold and 0.76% copper. Total gold production was 116,359 ounces, ie, 3,619 kg (Noble *et al.*, 2012). Between the two mines, almost a million ounces of gold and 20,000 tonnes of copper were obtained.

Using gold from the last ingot produced, smelted on December 20, 2006, a medal commemorating the cessation of the operation was coined by the company Rio Narcea Gold Mines. It was a replica of an aureus, a Roman gold coin, from Titus Flavius Vespasianus' time, whose original was recovered during the investigations of the mining area. These medals, of which 200 numbered copies were made, had the initials RN and were distributed in leather bags made by the Asociación de Creadores de Moda del Principado de Asturias.

The first gold ingot cast by the company on 25 February 1998, 2 kg in weight, is also conserved, and it was auctioned to benefit the municipalities of Salas and Belmonte in January 2007, being acquired by Cajastur. The main cause of the cessation of mining at Carlés, in which there were still significant reserves of ore, was that it was too small to be operated profitably independently after work stopped at the El Valle-Boinás mine. Rio Narcea Gold Mines stopped work at the latter due to problems caused by poor conditions underground, combined with the low gold content of the ore, and also to the refusal of the regional authorities to authorise operations at the Salave gold deposit, which they had been investigating in previous years. In 2007, the mining properties of Rio Narcea Gold Mines were acquired by Lunding Mining, who were mainly interested in the copper and nickel mine at Aguablanca, in Badajoz, so they almost immediately sold the gold mines, together with the ore processing plant, to Kinbauri Spain S.L.U., a subsidiary of Kinbauri Gold Corp. In September 2009, Orvana Minerals Corp. acquired ownership of Kinbauri Gold Corp, and consequently, its Spanish subsidiary and the Carlés mine.

Orvana investigated the mineralized zones and partially exploited Carlés North and Carlés East, calculating reserves of 485,000 tons of ore, containing 66,400 ounces of gold. They also examined other unexploited mineralizations, calculating for Northwest Carlés the possible extraction of 189,000 tons of ore containing 25,450 ounces of gold. Overall, between proven and probable reserves, the production estimates for Carlés were over one million tonnes of ore, with 3.5 grams of gold per ton (Wheeler *et al.*, 2010). In 2010, work was done to improve the facilities, and in 2011 they began producing ore again and processing it on a commercial scale. According to the company, in 2011, 9,336 ounces of gold were obtained from the El Valle-Belmonte and Carlés mines, 42,864 ounces in 2012 and 65,992 ounces in 2013. That year 197,768 ounces of silver and 6.6 million pounds of copper were also recovered.

The El Valle and Carles Boinás mines and the processing plant are currently in operation. Due to the decrease in the reserve estimates, the company announced in mid-August 2014 the temporary closure of the Carles mine later that year. The 65 workers of Carlés will be transferred to Boinás, increasing the latter's production but also shortening its lifespan.

Geology

The Carlés skarn was created by the intrusion of monzogranite (granodiorite), medium-grained, with abundant plagioclase into the limestones and dolomites of the Lower Devonian Rañecer Formation (Arcos *et al.*, 1996). The intrusion has a laccolith morphology, and the outcrop has an area of approximately 200 x 500 meters. The skarn has a semicircular shape, bordering the granodiorite pluton, bounded by the river Narcea. The skarn is more developed in the eastern area, where it reaches a thickness of up to 50 meters. In the W part of the intrusion, the thickness is less than 20 meters (Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000). Exoskarn predominates, with the endoskarn being a band of a few tens of centimeters at most. In the E, NE and W zones the skarn is of the calcium type, but in the N zone the intrusion has affected a dolomitic layer, the Nieva Formation, producing a magnesium skarn of about 2 meters thickness (Martin Izard *et al.* 2000). Using the K-Ar method, an age of 289 million years was calculated for the skarn (Arcos *et al.*, 1996).

The presence of minerals on the skarn surface was quite obvious, and Schulz (1858) already indicated the existence in "Carlés, near the river Narcea" of arsenopyrite, feldspar, amphibole and garnet, in the neighboring Devonian limestone. The main associations observed in the skarn are, according to Paniagua (1998), from the granodiorite outwards:

- Garnet (grossular-andradite), pyroxene (diopside-hedenbergite), feldspar and quartz.

Geological map and aerial photograph of the Carlés area, with the concession boundaries. The Carlés East open pit is partially restored.

Medal commemorating the closure of the mine and processing plant of Rio Narcea Gold Mines, coined in 2007. On the reverse it has the letters RN and an individual number. Its composition is 76% gold, 20% silver and 4% copper.

The current workings have exposed a portion of the ancient Roman galleries. Photo by Agustin Sanz.

- Garnet, pyroxene and amphibole (hastingsite-ferropargasite and ferroactinolite)
- Garnet and pyroxene
- Garnet
- Banded hornfels and marble.

In the NE contact area, a hydrothermal mineralization was also developed, associated with a fracture of NNW-SSW direction, affecting the limestone, the monzogranite and skarn. Various sulfides and sulfosalts appear in veins besides quartz and calcite (Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000).

Mineralogy

Carlés has several types of mineralization. The most important from an economic point of view is calcium exoskarn, with garnet and pyroxene as the most abundant components and copper and gold sulfides as economically valuable minerals. There is also a later hydrothermal mineralization, which gave rise to two large veins rich in antimony ores. The variety of sulphides contained in both the skarn and in the hydrothermal veins lead to a high number of mineral species produced by supergene alteration.

Open pit workings in Carlés North. Summer 2003.

Open pit in Carlés North, currently inactive, with entrances to the underground workings. July 2014.

Gold - Silver

Au - Ag

In the Carlés mine, gold, as gold-silver alloy (electrum), appears associated with chalcopyrite, arsenopyrite, bornite and a long series of rare sulphides in mineralized veins in the exoskarn (Arcos *et al.*, 1996). The alloy composition ranges from grains in which silver is dominant (up to 80%) to those where the dominant element is gold (up to 88%). Grains in which gold is dominant are associated mainly with antimony sulfosalts, whereas those in which silver is dominant are associated with argentiferous bornite and bismuth sulfosalts (Paniagua, 1998). Gold is distributed at the quite irregularly: the content in the quartz and feldspar skarn is low, whereas it is high in the skarn with amphiboles, especially in the outer part, where it appears in concentrations up to 25 g/t (Martin Izard *et al.*, 1993). The presence of copper minerals is also essential for gold, and gold is absent in associations in which there is no chalcopyrite or bornite. The grain size is usually very small, less than 10 microns in the case of inclusions in löllingite or arsenopyrite (Loredo and Garcia, 1988), being only visible with reflected light microscopy.

Occasionally, however, specimens with millimetric grains, visible to the naked eye, included in small masses of bornite, were found in the underground mine of Carlés East.

Gold. Arborescent form (1 mm) in bornite. Carlés East mine.

Bornite Cu_5FeS_4

Bornite is one of the most abundant metallic minerals in the Carlés skarn. It is deposited together with chalcopyrite and gold, in a later stage after löllingite formation.

It appears as masses that can reach several centimeters in size, associated with chalcopyrite and magnetite. Only very occasionally rounded crystals of millimeter size can be found within quartz in the underground workings of Carlés East, on dolomite crystals in vugs in the marbles of the open pit in Carlés North.

Chalcopyrite CuFeS_2

In the Carlés skarn chalcopyrite is generally the most abundant sulfide after arsenopyrite, but they do not seem to be directly related. It appears forming veins of different sizes in the exoskarn area (Arcos *et al.*, 1996). Also as small masses and disseminations in the hornfels. Within the calcite, very rough and fissured crystals of chalcopyrite of centimetric size sometimes appear. Frequently associated with chalcocite and covellite, formed as an alteration product, and in some areas also with löllingite or pyrrhotite. Occasionally very coarse crystals can be found in vugs, associated with arsenopyrite crystals.

Metastibnite Sb_2S_3

It has been found very occasionally, as spheroidal crusts over stibnite.

Stibnite Sb_2S_3

Stibnite is relatively common in the hydrothermal veins of Carlés North. It appears as granular masses and sometimes coarsely crystalline, with monocrystalline centimetric areas with obvious exfoliation. Within these masses there is spathic calcite filling voids in which acicular or bacillary crystals of stibnite up to 2 cm long are trapped, forming divergent or disordered aggregates. They may be seen by removing calcite with an acid. In these “vugs”, along with stibnite crystals, sphalerite and arsenopyrite appear. In some areas, the stibnite is altered in part to valentinite, covering holes in the primary mineral.

Stibnite has also been found as spherules formed of very fine acicular crystals grouped divergently in some areas of the marble. These spherules, locally abundant, have a diameter of one or two millimeters, and are generally not completely filled with stibnite. Sometimes stibnite is wholly or partially altered to valentinite. Another way in which stibnite appears is as small inclusions in calcite crystals

Sphalerite $(\text{Zn}, \text{Fe}) \text{S}$

Sphalerite appears in the hydrothermal veins associated with jamesonite and especially with stibnite. It appears as centimetric crystalline masses or as well defined spinel-law twin single crystals, which generally have a maximum ridge size of several millimeters.

It has a relatively dark brown color. Yellowish sphalerite, in fine grained masses, appears along with stibnite. It has further been found as microcrystals over dolomite crystals in vugs within marbles.

Sphalerite crystals (2 mm edge) with stibnite. Carlés North.

Group of stibnite crystals with sphalerite crystals, 3.5 cm long. Carlés North.

that cover some cracks in the marble, which makes the calcite opaque or black. Over these crystals, flat prismatic groups of stibnite, bright and well-defined, may appear with a length of a few millimeters.

Pyrrhotite $\text{Fe}_{(1-x)}\text{S}$ ($x = 0 - 0,2$)

Pyrrhotite is a relatively abundant component in the skarn forming the gold deposit of Carlés (Paniagua, 1998). In the old mine tailings, located along the road between Soto and Vega de los Infantes and river Narcea, short prismatic crystals up to 1 cm were found. In recent mining it has appeared as masses several centimetres in size, associated with magnetite, chalcopyrite and other sulphides.

Galena PbS

Galena is part of the post-skarn hydrothermal mineralization, and there are at least two generations. The first one appears as rather altered crystalline masses, very coarse grained, with decimetric size, in the most external zones to cerussite and anglesite. In these masses sometimes geodes with octahedral galena crystals appear. The crystals are up to a centimeter on edge, altered on the outside and sometimes are covered by a thick crust of cerussite or are even partially pseudomorphed. The other generation, produced by remobilization, appears as arborescent clusters of tiny cuboctahedral crystals in dolomite vugs, over tapestries of pink dolomite crystals.

Octahedral galena microcrystals. Carlés North.

Octahedral galena crystals coated with cerussite. Carlés North. Edge of the octahedron, 1 cm.

Molybdenite MoS_2

According to research conducted by mining companies, molybdenite appears to be particularly abundant in an area located in the NW of the granodiorite intrusion, in an area that has not yet been exploited. Molybdenite also appears in an amphibolite zone related to a fracture with NNW-SSE direction. Molybdenite occupies the place of copper minerals in the upper area of skarn (Martin Izard *et al.*, 1998). It is occasionally found as small irregular lamellar crystals within quartz in the Carlés East area. It also appears, along with quartz, in the small quarry operated on altered granodiorite, before the modern gold mine began operating.

Irregular lamellar crystals of molybdenite in quartz. Carlés North. Largest group, 4 mm.

Marcasite FeS_2

It appears as very small microcrystals, usually forming twins over dolomite crystals in the marble vugs. It is sometimes accompanied by epitaxial overgrowths of pyrite. In skarn, the presence of this mineral is reported, associated with pyrite (Rua Figueroa *et al.*, 1987).

Marcasite twin. Carlés North.

Pyrite crystals, 1 mm on edge, cube and dodecahedron combination, on dolomite. Carlés North.

Cubic pyrite microcrystals on dolomite. Carlés North.

Pyrite FeS_2

In hydrothermal veins, pyrite occurs quite often as one centimeter crystals generally grouped by combining pentagonododecahedral cubes. It is associated with arsenopyrite and quartz. Crystals formed by the combination of cube and octahedron can also be found, much less frequently, with the octahedron faces very rough. In the marbles, pyrite occurs within cavities, as microcrystals over dolomite crystal druses. These microcrystals take different forms in each cavity, but the most abundant are those formed by combining cube with dodecahedron (and sometimes also with small octahedral faces). Some are comprised exclusively by the cube form, and more rarely by the octahedron or with only minor modifications of other faces. Pseudomorphs after pyrrhotite crystals also appear, small and tabular and with hexagonal contour.

Löllingite FeAs_2

Löllingite appears in a network of thick veins between centimetric and millimetric size which intersect the quartz monzogranite near the skarn. It is associated with arsenopyrite, chalcopyrite and molybdenite, in addition to quartz, feldspar and carbonates (Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000). Löllingite is also sometimes found in the skarn, accompanying bornite and chalcopyrite (Paniagua, 1998). This mineralization can reach up to 2 meters long and 20 cm thick within the garnet-pyroxene-amphibole zone (Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000). The presence of inclusions in the arsenopyrite skarn has also been reported (Loredó and García Iglesias, 1988). Löllingite also appears associated with actinolite in the replacements in the contact between marbles and exoskarn (Arcos *et al.*, 1996). Although the studies cited above generally refer to this mineral on a microscopic scale, Löllingite visibly to the naked eye can be found too, such as grains or multicentimetric masses or as millimetric crystals associated with the aforementioned minerals and also with magnetite. During the exploitation of Carlés Nortés, specimens in which löllingite appears as groups up to 10 centimetres size, consisting of rough crystals with lenticular habit and an individual size up to 2 cm inside a mass of crystalline calcite were found. Along with löllingite, masses and aggregates of small crystals of diopside-

hedenbergite can be found, varying in color between nearly colorless clear green and dark green, depending on the iron content, and with either being dominant.

Löllingite. Aggregate of leafy crystals, 2.5 cm high. Carlés North open pit. Löllingite crystal was included in crystalline calcite, which has been partly removed with acid.

Gudmundite FeSbS

Gudmundite is very occasionally found as aggregates of microcrystals over dolomite tapestries in cavities in the marbles.

Gudmundite microcrystals on quartz. Carlés North. Field of view: 6 mm.

Arsenopyrite FeAsS

The presence of arsenopyrite in the area was very evident in some outcrops before modern mining operations began. Herrgen (1801) already indicated the existence of "arsenical pyrite" in Salas. In this site arsenopyrite is quite abundant, especially in the replacement area of amphibole and arsenopyrite in contact between the skarn and the marbles (Arcos *et al.*, 1996). Arsenopyrite also appears in quartz veins within granodiorite, together with minor amounts of other sulfides (Rua Figueroa *et al.*, 1987). Arsenopyrite is often found in the skarn as single crystals of a size up to a centimeter or as groups of crystals, sometimes in parallel growth inside quartz or in cavities filled with calcite crystals. When calcite is removed with an acid, very interesting specimens can be obtained, with well defined crystals. Arsenopyrite also appears as masses of up to 20 centimeters in diameter, with small holes with crystals of the same mineral.

Associated with arsenopyrite are quartz, löllingite, native bismuth, bismuthinite, chalcopyrite and other sulfides (Loredo and García Iglesias, 1988). Arsenopyrite is monoclinic, but the crystal habit is pseudo-rhombic due to twinning on a submicroscopic or microscopic scale on (100) and (101). Crystals may have tabular or prismatic development. The tabular habit is preferably formed by {101}, with the termination {120} and {010}, very often heavily rounded or knurled, so that the faces of the two figures are merged. The crystals of prismatic habit generally correspond to the {013} striated faces. In the Carlés East area complex microcrystals of arsenopyrite were found in small vugs with feldspar.

Arsenopyrite crystal from Carlés. FOV 15mm.

Group of arsenopyrite crystals in parallel growth. Carlés North. Specimen height, 3 cm.

Kermesite Sb_2S_2O

Kermesite is found occasionally in Carlés North as divergent aggregates of acicular or filiform crystals with a length of up to a centimeter, with the dark red reflection typical of this mineral. It is associated with arsenopyrite and sphalerite crystals, and less frequently with stibnite, in a matrix of crystalline calcite with some quartz. In some kermesite crystals extremely small crystals of anglesite were found, visible only with the scanning electron microscope.

Kermesite with anglesite. Carlés North.

Kermesite in calcite. Carlés North. FOV 2 cm.

Bournonite $PbCuSbS_3$

Bournonite has appeared as masses of several millimeters, associated with tetrahedrite and stibnite in the hydrothermal mineralization in Carlés North. It has also been found as small aggregates of twinned crystals, generally with slightly rounded bright but well defined edges, over carpets of dolomite and quartz crystals in the marble cavities. Rather larger pyrite crystals are associated with it.

Twinned bournonite crystals on dolomite. Carlés North. Crystal group size, 3 mm.

Tetrahedrite $Cu_6[Cu_4(Fe,Zn)_2]Sb_4S_{11}$

In the massive skarn tetrahedrite is very abundant, accompanied by arsenopyrite, bornite, chalcopyrite and wittichenite. In many cases containing bismuth, belonging to the variety called annivite (Paniagua, 1998). Loredó and García (1988) indicate the presence of tennantite in Carlés in the samples obtained before the mine operations started.

Tetrahedrite can be found in Carlés North as crystals of a size between a millimeter and a centimeter. It appears inside the vugs in massive hydrothermal ore veins, or in vugs associated with quartz, pyrite and occasionally arsenopyrite. The crystals are generally irregular and corroded, faces and rounded edges, thick striations and stepped growths, but with a high gloss. They are formed by the tetrahedron or by the combination of the tetrahedron with tristetrahedron.

Tetrahedrite with pyrite. Carlés North. Size of the tetrahedrite crystals, 2 mm.

Jamesonite $Pb_4FeSb_6S_{14}$

The most notable find of jamesonite made in Spain so far occurred in the summer of 2002, during the operation of the Carlés North mine. Jamesonite, very abundant locally, was found in fibrous crystalline form associated with sphalerite and pyrite, and also some secondary minerals. It appears in the contact between the skarn mineralization and the marbles in the area closest to the contact. The mineral fills veins up to 3 cm thick, with transversely oriented fibers.

In some areas elongated crystals up to 2 cm in length and 2 mm thick appear, disorderly grouped, forming fan-shaped groups in the veins or inside carbonates. Very rarely coarsely acicular free crystals have also been found inside small vugs.

It can also be found in bornite, accompanied by other rare sulfides, as inclusions visible only by reflected light microscopy (Paniagua, 1998) and inside arsenopyrite (Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000).

*Fibrous jamesonite, pyrite and arsenopyrite.
Carlés North. FOV 7 cm.*

Zinkenite $Pb_9Sb_{22}S_{42}$

Zinkenite is occasionally found in Carlés North as prismatic microcrystals associated with stibnite, which is indistinguishable to the naked eye.

Zinkenite. Carlés North.

Fluorite CaF_2

Fluorite is a very scarce mineral in Carlés, having only occasionally been found as small crystalline masses associated with molybdenite and quartz.

Hematite Fe_2O_3

Hematite is a rare mineral in this deposit, although it has been found in the form of microcrystals over quartz or over arsenopyrite in vugs covered with quartz crystals. The most notable aspect of these microcrystals is their pseudo-cubic habit, since they are formed by the rhombohedron $\{01\bar{1}1\}$, with two vertices modified by very small $\{0001\}$ faces. It is also occasionally found as lamellar crystal rosettes accompanied by quartz and calcite.

Senarmontite Sb_2O_3

The Carlés gold mine is the most notable site for this species in Spain, and the only one where crystals visible to the naked eye can be found (Calvo, 2009). Senarmontite appears in a particular area of the higher mining works along with antimony sulfides and sulfosalts inside marble, as an alteration product of stibnite. It appears forming octahedral crystals of millimetric size, well-defined, single or associated in parallel growth. These crystals are usually colorless or white, bright and they often have sulfide acicular inclusions, possibly zinkenite or stibnite. In some cases the abundance of inclusions makes the crystals black and opaque. Senarmontite crystals appear in a spongy matrix of quartz and sulfides, where traces of the alteration process are evident. The crystalline calcite that accompanies stibnite usually has almost completely disappeared, leaving rhombohedral shaped gaps on the walls. In these gaps, with flat walls covered with quartz, senarmontite crystals are found, and sometimes valentine along with it.

*Octahedral crystals of senarmontite, 1.5 mm on edge.
Carlés North.*

Magnetite $\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{Fe}^{3+}_2\text{O}_4$

Magnetite is very abundant in the Carlés skarn, known since ancient times. Toreno (1785) indicates that in Carlés there is “de azero” mineral, located from Mediodía to Levante. He also indicates that it appears mixed with copper ore. Since the modern Carlés mine is situated about hundred meters southeast of the village, it is clear that he was referring to Toreno. It could have been possibly extracted some time ago, even in Roman times, along with copper minerals and gold. One of the concessions of the mine is called the “Magnética” precisely because of the presence of this mineral. Magnetite is found most abundantly in the outermost zone of the skarn, along with garnet-pyroxene-amphibole, associated with chalcopyrite, bornite and löllingite, forming stratiform masses (Martin Izard *et al.*, 1993). Magnetite was formed in the retrograde skarn stage before the sulphides (Fernandez and White, 1992, Martin Izard *et al.*, 1993) and it usually appears as granular compact masses.

Magnetite crystals are very scarce in this locality, but they can be occasionally found at the higher open pit with the dodecahedron {011} as the dominant figure, modified by small octahedral faces {111}.

All the faces of the rhombohedron are strongly striated, with the striations parallel to the faces of the octahedron, due to the oscillatory growth of these two forms. These crystals, with a size somewhat bigger than a centimeter, appear on massive magnetite, trapped inside a talc-like material. Magnetite also occurs inside cavities within the garnet masses, as tiny octahedral crystals of smooth and shiny faces, forming parallel growths in two

directions, mimicking the classic hematite “iron roses”. Possibly it is a pseudomorph of this mineral. Along with magnetite, pyrite crystals and various silicates appear.

The cavities are filled by crystalline calcite.

To the south of the skarn zone, across the road and the river Narcea, magnetite appears in the metamorphic contact zone between the granodiorite and the ferruginous Silurian sandstones (Fernandez and White, 1992).

Striated crystals of magnetite from Carlés North.

Central crystal size, 8 mm.

Magnetite crystal formed by rhombic dodecahedron {011} with striated faces due to the oscillating growth of octahedron, modified by small octahedron faces.

Woodruffite

Woodruffite has occasionally been found in the Carlés North workings as small nodules with internal laminated structure, with a dark brown color, almost black, with little luster on the outside and relatively bright in the fracture surfaces.

It is associated with chapmanite in the marbles, in the alteration zone of sulfides (Calvo, 2009).

Woodruffite is a relatively rare mineral, known only in about a dozen locations in the world, in most cases in earthy form, associated with other manganese oxides.

Woodruffite. Carlés North. FOV 3 mm.

For this species, the specimens from Carlés can be considered significant for their quality.

Oxiplumboromeite

This mineral, known until recently as bindheimite, appears in Carlés as crusts or powdery compact masses, with a bright yellow color, as an alteration product of sulfosalts, especially jamesonite, present on the veins encased in the marbles of the superficial area of the site.

Also associated with cerussite, in small amounts, as an alteration product of galena, which in this case would contain antimony as inclusions. Along with oxiplumboromeite, small unaltered arsenopyrite crystals and sphalerite crystals can be found.

Quartz SiO_2

Quartz is found in the hydrothermal mineralization as gemmy or slightly tinted crystals, colorless, up to 2 centimeters in length, within crystalline calcite. It can occasionally be found as small crystals smaller than 5 mm, with a very pale amethyst color. In addition to calcite, it appears particularly with arsenopyrite, as small crystals.

In vugs in the marbles biterminated crystals of milky quartz occasionally appear, similar to the previous ones in size, on carpets of small pink dolomite crystals. Quartz also appears covering the walls of some cavities.

*Amethystine quartz. Carlés North.
Crystal size, 4 mm.*

Quartz. Carlés North. Crystal length, 2 cm.

Valentinite Sb_2O_3

Valentinite is a relatively common mineral in the upper zone of the hydrothermal veins produced by the alteration of stibnite.

It appears as aggregates of prismatic crystals up to 3 mm long, striated and with irregular terminations.

The crystals have a white, or slightly beige color, with pearly or silky luster. In some cases the valentinite crystals are big enough that the fracture structures produced by its perfect cleavage can be clearly distinguished.

More common than the well defined prismatic crystals of valentinite are the pseudoprisms,

Valentinite crystals, 2 mm long in stibnite. Carlés North.

composed of clusters of subparallel acicular crystals. At the ends the needles are further apart since in the center the crystals are larger than those of the periphery. Valentinite appears inside the vugs within the sulfide complex associations, where arsenopyrite predominates. In fact, in the vugs where there is valentinite, it is also common to find microcrystals of arsenopyrite, bright and without any visible alteration.

Calcite CaCO_3

Calcite is a very abundant mineral. It is the last mineral formed in the vugs in the skarn, and it usually fills them completely. It appears in spathic form or very coarsely crystallised, and is colorless. It can also be white or green or chocolate colored due to the presence of silicates and iron oxides as inclusions. It also fills the gaps in the hydrothermal veins, including most of the sulfides. Also it has occasionally been found in the form of single crystals. The bigger specimens, with white crystals up to 4 inches in length, were found in the lower ramp, covering cavities up to 1.5 meters in diameter. These crystals were formed by a combination of the negative rhombohedron $\{01\bar{1}2\}$ and a sharp positive rhombohedron, probably $\{160\bar{1}61\}$. Furthermore calcite appears as small black crystals due to the presence of stibnite inclusions (Calvo, 2012).

*Calcite (1mm crystals) with stibnite inclusions.
Carlés North.*

Brucite Mg(OH)_2

Some areas of the metamorphic aureole of the marbles of Carlés are gray and, along with dolomite and calcite, they contain abundant brucite grains which are probably formed by supergene hydration of periclase.

Goethite $\text{Fe}^{3+}\text{O(OH)}$

As well as forming small botryoidal crusts and earthy iron oxides, goethite can be found as acicular crystals of less than 1 millimeter in length, in spherulitic habits. Also these same needles appear as inclusions within calcite crystals.

Dolomite $\text{CaMg(CO}_3)_2$

In the dolomitic marble in the Carlés North open pit, many vugs internally coated with small dolomite crystals appeared. Those crystals have a more or less intense white or pink color, with the typical curved shape of this mineral, about 1 millimeter on edge. They cover the internal walls and form arborescent growths. Various other minerals formed on top of dolomite during a late hydrothermal mobilization. Standing out for their size, up to two centimeters, milky quartz crystals. Also hematite microcrystals, pyrite and many other sulfides.

*Dolomite and quartz (crystal 1 cm in height).
Carlés North.*

Siderite FeCO_3

In the fissures of the altered skarn siderite can be occasionally found as tiny beads of brown color, translucent and shiny, formed by groupings of curved microcrystals.

Siderite microspherules. Carlés North.

Aragonite CaCO_3

Although it is not very abundant, aragonite can be found in both the skarn and in the hydrothermal ores of Carlés North. In the skarn it can appear in veins in the garnet, over a colloform material, as divergent aggregates each formed by subparallel crystals. In the hydrothermal ores aragonite appears as clusters of very fine radiating acicular microcrystals forming colorless spherules or carpets with felted appearance. These crystals appear in veins in the löllingite and arsenopyrite-rich ore zone, and are sometimes associated with chapmanite.

Also small botryoidal coatings with compact radiated internal structure can be found. In these cases, often extremely fine aragonite microcrystals can occur individually on the surface. Also relatively well defined aragonite acicular crystals up to two millimeters in length can be found, forming divergent aggregates inside monzogranitic gaps, which had been coated previously by crystalline masses and calcite crystals. Very sharp crystals have also been found, accompanying hörnesite and hydromagnesite.

Aragonite. Carlés North.

Aragonite. Carlés North. FOV 2 cm.

Cerussite PbCO_3

Cerussite is a supergene alteration product of galena in the vein ores. In Carlés North it can be found covering octahedral galena crystals, and partially pseudomorphing it. It also appears as tapestries of millimeter twinned crystals, pyramid-like, colorless or gray, in the walls of the holes of massive galena crystals. Also as brilliant white crystalline aggregates, where only some faces of the crystals can be seen, within a rusty earthy material.

Twinned cerussite crystals inside a cavity in altered galena. Carlés North open pit. Size of each crystal, 2 mm.

Malachite

Malachite was quite abundant in the superficial alteration, along with other secondary copper minerals, and it was likely it attracted attention in ancient times.

In the modern Carlés North workings, malachite has been found forming thin botryoidal crusts, with small spherules of azurite on top. Sometimes crusts and beads are coated with a layer of cryptocrystalline silica almost invisible to the naked eye (Calvo, 2012).

Azurite $\text{Cu}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$

The presence of this mineral, in the joints of metamorphosed limestones, in outcrops located about 200 meters S of the village of Carlés already caught the attention of the first researchers who investigated this site (García de Figuerola, and Peña, 1964). More recently, azurite has been found in the upper reservoir of Carlés North, occasionally as tabular microcrystals grouped like tiny roses on altered chalcopyrite or on malachite spherules. It also appears associated with chrysocolla (Calvo, 2012).

Malachite and azurite. Carlés North. FOV 2 cm.

Pyroaurite $\text{Mg}_6\text{Fe}^{3+}_2(\text{OH})_{16}[\text{CO}_3]\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Pyroaurite is occasionally found as crusts with pearlescent white color, associated with serpentine in the open pit in Carlés North. It has also been found as thinner and dull layers and in the dolomitic marbles of the same area.

Pyroaurite. Carlés North. FOV 2 cm.

Hydromagnesite $\text{Mg}_5(\text{CO}_3)_4(\text{OH})_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

It appeared in the open pit in Carlés North as spherules a few millimeters in diameter. White, with finely radiated internal structure and with the outer surface coated with very small lamellar crystals, which gave them a silky luster, on a crust of aragonite crystals. It is associated with aggregates of hörnesite crystals of a much larger size.

Hydromagnesite spherules (2 mm diameter). Carlés North.

Apatite $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{F}$

The presence of this mineral was reported as a product of late hydrothermal activity in fractures (Martin Izard *et al.*, 1998).

Hydromagnesite crystals. Carlés North.

Brochantite $\text{Cu}_4(\text{SO}_4)(\text{OH})_6$

Brochantite appears in the alteration zone of the Carlés North ores as poorly defined crystals of lamellar habit, sometimes lenticular or wedge-shaped, and sometimes almost acicular, with a deep green color, forming aggregates or associations of small divergent sheaves. It is associated with tyrolite on iron oxides with relics of chalcopyrite (Calvo, 2014).

Brochantite. Carlés North.

Brochantite. Carlés North. FOV 1 cm.

Anglesite PbSO_4

Anglesite appears as an alteration product of galena. Sometimes as crusts, mixed with cerussite, or as elongated crystals up to a centimeter in length, colorless or slightly yellowish, sometimes transparent and bright. The crystals, which are located in gaps within crystalline masses of galena, are formed by the combination of {401} and {100} as dominant faces, terminated by {011} faces, and often also with small modifications of {221} faces (Calvo, 2014).

Crystal habit of anglesite from Carlés, with rhombic prism {401} and pinacoid {100} as main forms.

Prismatic anglesite crystals in a galena vug. Carlés North. Largest crystal, 8mm.

Conichalcite $\text{CaCu}(\text{AsO}_4)(\text{OH})$

This mineral is very scarce at Carlés. It occasionally occurs as thin botryoidal crusts, with a relatively smooth and shiny surface, grass green colored, typical of this mineral. Among the secondary minerals, conichalcite is only associated with small beads of goethite.

Conichalcite. Carlés North. FOV 1 cm.

Mimetite. Carlés Nord.

Mimetite on cerussite and galena. Carlés North. FOV 1 cm.

Mimetite $Pb_5(AsO_4)_3Cl$

Mimetite has occasionally been found in the altered dyke mineralization. It appears as yellowish or green crystalline crusts on galena or as very thin coatings on cerussite crystals. Sometimes the cerussite has disappeared, leaving paramorphs of this mineral. The coatings are formed by the combination of parallel growth prismatic micro crystals with a length of one tenth of a millimeter.

Scorodite $FeAsO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$

Scorodite is relatively frequent and can be seen in the crack-free surfaces of the skarn, formed by alteration of löllingite and arsenopyrite, forming two types of associations. The first can be found associated with pharmacosiderite and unidentified arsenate, compact and bright yellow, as crystals usually with a very dark greenish brown color, forming interpenetrating cones or flat aggregates. Individual crystals can reach a size of two millimeters and are very simple, with a pyramidal morphology with {111} as the only visible form, with somewhat curved faces. In other specimens, scorodite appears as transparent microcrystals with a pale yellow or orange color, associated with arseniosiderite.

These crystals are more complex with, besides the {111} face, faces {001} and {201}. In the latter case they are quite variable in size and may become very important. Occasionally it can also be found coating and pseudomorphing parasymplectite needle-like crystals and rosettes.

Scorodite crystals. Carlés North. FOV 1 cm. Below detail in SEM photo.

Scorodite crystals from Carlés, on the left the simplest one, formed by a bipyramid, and on the right the most complex one, with small pinacoid and prism faces.

Parasymplesite $\text{Fe}^{2+}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$

This mineral appears inside cracks in the mineralization as a supergene alteration product of löllingite. It can take various forms, depending on the size and location of the cracks, and possibly on the speed of growth. In most cases it appears as formations of radiated lamellar crystals elongated along the [001] direction, up to a centimeter in length, with a quite characteristic very dark blue-green color. In the narrow cracks, which are the majority, the rosettes of crystals are in contact with the two surfaces, so only the perfect cleavage planes corresponding to {010} can be seen in the surfaces. Its appearance sometimes resembles some pyroxene and amphibole rosettes, and since it appears in a dark matrix, probably it has been gone unnoticed in many specimens.

Very occasionally some fissure is wide enough to enable the growth of individual millimetric sized crystals. In this case, the dominant figure is {010}, with the contour formed by {100} and {111} faces and minor modifications of {201}. Specimens of parasymplesite coated with arseniosiderite or pharmacosiderite have been found, and some of them partly pseudomorphed to the latter mineral.

It also appears as feathery and lamellar crystal aggregates or as very fine acicular crystals. In this case they have a relatively silky luster and a pale blue color and can form spherules of acicular crystals or appear as very elongated lamellar crystals. The lamellar crystals can appear as individuals or forming compact spherules, with blue dark color by reflected light and dirty yellow in the case of transparent single crystals. These spherules are usually the last mineral to form in the fissures, appearing on pharmacosiderite druses.

Parasymplesite. Carlés North. FOV 6 mm.

Morphology of a tabular crystal of parasymplesite.

Hörnesite $\text{Mg}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Hörnesite appears as thin tabular crystals, colorless or white, translucent, growing subparallel as sheaves on crusts of aragonite microcrystals, produced by löllingite alteration. The only visible faces are those corresponding to {010}, even if the external shape indicates the presence of {100}, {201} and {20 $\bar{1}$ }. It is associated with hydromagnesite, forming spheres of lamellar crystals. The Carlés crystals are very large considering the usual size of this species, which is also relatively rare. Hörnesite associated with hydromagnesite has also been found at other localities, such as Fiano quarries in Nocera, Campania (Italy) (Zambonini, 1919).

Hörnesite tabular crystal, with the pinacoid {010} as main face.

Group of divergent hörnesite crystals (3 mm). Carlés North.

Hörnesite crystals. Carlés North.

Euchroite $\text{Cu}_2(\text{AsO}_4)(\text{OH})\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Euchroite can be found at Carlés North very occasionally as millimetric size crystals, single or grouped, bright with a grass-green color on chrysocolla crusts. In the collected specimens it is not associated with any other species. Crystals have a simple morphology, with tabular habit, with {010} as the most developed face. This face often presents striations or staggered parallel growths. Euchroite is a relatively rare mineral, and this is the first locality for Spain. Unfortunately very few specimens were recovered.

Morphology of a crystal of euchroite. Carlés North.

Group of euchroite microcrystals on chrysocolla. Carlés North. FOV 4 mm.

Tyrolite $\text{Ca}_2\text{Cu}_9(\text{AsO}_4)_4(\text{CO}_3)(\text{OH})_8\cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Tyrolite was relatively abundant in the upper zone of the locality, produced by supergene alteration of the rich sulfide skarn. It appeared as spherulitic aggregates formed by very small and thin individual crystals, coating cracks in the oxidized skarn or even as quite friable masses formed mainly by iron oxides. It has been occasionally found associated with brochantite and malachite.

Tyrolite microcrystals (size 1 mm). Carlés North. Below: details tyrolite crystals in SEM photo. Carlés North.

Pharmacosiderite

This mineral has been found in Carlés North as crystals smaller than a millimeter with two distinct morphologies. Pharmacosiderite crystals that are associated with dark crystals of scorodite and with an unidentified yellow arsenate, have cubic form, without modifications. They form parallel growths and are not very bright and have a very dark green color, almost black. Also in this association of minerals pharmacosiderite crystals with orange color can be found. Pharmacosiderite that appears associated with scorodite and yellow arseniosiderita is usually green, from light to very dark olive in tone, almost black, and is formed by the combination of cube and tetrahedron.

Cubic microcrystals of pharmacosiderite (under 1 mm) with an unknown arsenate. Carlés North.

Below: SEM photo of a crystal of pharmacosiderite. Carlés North.

Pharmacosiderite crystal from Carlés North open pit, formed by combination of {100} and {111} faces.

Arseniosiderite $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}^{3+}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_3\text{O}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Arseniosiderite is widespread in the alteration zone in Carlés North, appearing as powder or scaly coatings in the fissures or, less frequently, as clusters of spherules or botryoidal crusts, with lamellar radiated internal structure and pearly luster. It can exhibit different shades of color, from yellow to deep orange, almost red.

Rosettes of arseniosiderite lamellar microcrystals.

Carlés North. FOV 9 mm.

Above: detail in SEM photo. Carlés North.

Unidentified arsenate

Associated with scorodite crystals and with pharmacosiderite, sometimes a compact mineral with intense yellow color occurs. Sometimes it has a slight waxy sheen, forming relatively thick crusts or isolated patches. Its composition corresponds to an iron arsenate with some calcium. Its X-ray diffraction spectrum does not match any known species. It is likely to be a new species, but it has not yet been characterized in detail.

X-ray diffraction of the unknown arsenate from Carlés North open pit, whose characteristics do not match those of any known species.

Unknown arsenate, pharmacosiderite and scorodite. Carlés North. 0,8 mm edge.

Grossular $\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_2(\text{SiO}_4)_3$ Andradite $\text{Ca}_3\text{Fe}_2(\text{SiO}_4)_3$

Garnet of the grossular - andradite series is a fundamental component of the Carlés skarn. It appears forming microcrystalline masses and also as well formed crystals. Microcrystalline masses have a dark brown color and a composition in which andradite usually dominates, although a significant proportion of grossular component can be found too, with grossular being sometimes even dominant. Euhedral garnet crystals show concentric zoned growth, in which case grossular always dominates, with contents between 54% and 84%, although in some cases andradite is slightly dominant in the central part of the crystals. Grossular also dominates (between 70% and 75%) in garnets that fill fractures or that partly replace those previously formed (Irzard Martin *et al.*, 2000). Grossular crystals that appear in vugs, often well formed, can reach a size of up to two centimeters, but usually they do not exceed a centimeter. They are formed by the dodecahedron {110} as the dominant form, these faces being smooth and bright, modified with smaller {211} faces of the trapezohedron, striated in the direction of its symmetrical diagonal. The trapezohedron faces can be very small, and in some crystals they can have different development, some smaller than others. Grossular crystals can have various

shades of reddish brown color, from dark brown to orange, and very occasionally they can have an iridescent metallic look. Occasionally skeletal growths have also been found, but even then in that case the faces of the crystals are well defined. In vugs with garnet crystals titanite can also appear, with plagioclase, pyroxene, amphibole and white crystalline calcite, which is the last mineral to form and fills the vugs completely. Garnet crystals often have cracks in the outer region, so that when calcite is removed, small fragments break off easily, leaving the crystals damaged.

Grossular garnet (5 mm) with calcite. Carlés North.

Forsterite Mg_2SiO_4

Forsterite appears, along with spinel, in the north zone of the Carlés mineralization, in which magnesium is especially abundant, forming bands with diopside and phlogopite is the first mineral to form (Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000).

Titanite $CaTi(SiO_4)O$

Titanite appears frequently in the skarn cavities as clusters of small lenticular crystals of light greenish brown color, with irregular morphology. The crystals form divergent associations or arborescent structures. It is associated with garnet, pyroxene and uralitized feldspar.

The geodes are completely filled with crystalline calcite, which must be removed with an acid to observe the other minerals present.

Leafy aggregates of titanite. Carlés North. FOV 1,1 cm.

Vesuvianite $(Ca,Na,\square)_{19}(Al,Mg,Fe^{3+})_{13}(\square,B,Al,Fe^{3+})_5(Si_2O_7)_4(SiO_4)_{10}(OH,F,O)_{10}$

Vesuvianite is not a very abundant mineral in Carlés. It has been found as bundles up to 3 centimeters size, consisting of bacillary coarse crystals grouped divergently, olive green or greenish brown, associated with garnet.

Sometimes crystals have a cavernous structure, being partially hollow.

Vesuvianite with garnet. Carlés North. Specimen height, 5 cm.

Datolite $Ca(HBSiO_5)$

It is found as white large grained masses associated with ferroactinolite and epidote in Carlés East skarn. Occasionally crystals with up to 2 centimeters have appeared, black and quite rough, after eliminating the calcite that fills the geodes.

Epidote $Ca_2(Al,Fe^{3+})(Si_2O_7)(SiO_4)O(OH)$

Epidote is relatively rare in the Carlés skarn, appearing as masses with coarsely fibrous structure, with green color, formed by bacillary crystals. It is associated with ferroactinolite and datolite, and with plagioclase pseudomorphs after scapolite crystals.

Allanite-(Ce) $(CaCe)(Al_2Fe^{2+})(Si_2O_7)(SiO_4)O(OH)$

Allanite-Ce is found in Carlés skarn as black crystals up to a centimeter in size, with different morphologies.

It appears inside cavities, in the massive mineralization, with hedenbergite crystals sometimes partially or completely uralitized, with sphene, feldspar and löllingite. These cavities, like all of the skarn, were subsequently filled with crystalline white calcite.

Allanite-Ce in calcite. Carlés East mine. Crystal, 5 mm.

Diopside $\text{CaMgSi}_2\text{O}_6$

Diopside occurs, with a pale green color, replacing garnet and forming alternating bands with it. In other cases, the dominant component is hedenbergite (Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000). In the northern part of the locality, in the magnesian skarn, diopside appears as fine-grained or coarse aggregates, sometimes replacing olivine. It is associated with phlogopite (Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000). It has also been found as small, very corroded white prismatic crystals associated with löllingite in vugs in the massive ore of Carlés North. These vugs were filled by crystalline calcite at a later stage.

Diopside with löllingite. Carlés North. FOV 2 cm.

Hornblende $\square(\text{Ca}_2)(\text{Fe}^{2+}_4\text{Al})(\text{AlSi}_7\text{O}_{22})(\text{OH})_2$

The composition of Carlés hornblendes is between hastingsite and ferropargasite (Martin Izard *et al.*, 1998). In the innermost part of the exoskarn there is a zone consisting of hastingsite with some potassium content, associated with magnetite and disseminated sulphides. This mineral has been used to calculate the age of the skarn (Arcos *et al.*, 1996).

Ferroactinolite

In Carlés, amphiboles are formed by replacement of pyroxene and garnet in the first retrograde alteration of the skarn, preferably in the inner and intermediate zone.

Amphiboles of actinolite-ferroactinolite type are formed after the other amphiboles and sulfides (Martin Izard *et al.*, 1998).

Generally ferroactinolite is the dominant component in this series (Arcos *et al.*, 1996).

*Ferroactinolite with datolite.
Carlés North. FOV 5,8 cm.*

Chrysotile $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5)(\text{OH})_4$

Chrysotile, of the clinochrysotile type, has been found forming fibrous veins a few millimeters thick, with the fibers perpendicular to the walls of the veins, in massive serpentine.

Hedenbergite $\text{CaFe}^{2+}\text{Si}_2\text{O}_6$

Hedenbergite is the dominant pyroxene in fracture fillings and cavities. It is dark green (Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000). Also found as large grains in the endoskarn area, or as veins that cut the diopside bands (Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000). In the skarn cavities it can be observed after removal of the crystalline calcite that filled the cavities at a later stage. It appears as very dark green crystals with prismatic habit and up to a centimeter in length. They have a square cross-section, and are formed by a combination of pinacoids $\{100\}$ and $\{010\}$, sometimes with small $\{110\}$ faces, and terminated by the pinacoid $\{001\}$ or more complex forms. They are associated with löllingite, garnet and feldspar, and are frequently transformed partially or totally into pyroxene.

*Hedenbergite crystals, 4 mm high, with löllingite.
Carlés North.*

Clinochlore

Although it is not a particularly abundant mineral in Carlés, it appears as masses formed by interpenetrating lamellar dark green crystals, mainly associated with magnetite and arsenopyrite. It is occasionally found as small sharp crystals, with this mineral's usual hexagonal shape, in cavities inside magnetite crystals, with diopside and ferroactinolite crystals.

Magnetite, diopside, ferroactinolite and clinocllore. Carlés North. FOV 2 cm.

Sepiolite $\text{Mg}_4(\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{15})(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Sepiolite has occasionally appeared as thin lamellar crusts with fibrous texture, like scraps of paper, with a light brown color, over small colorless crystals of dolomite. Microcrystals of the latter mineral can also be found growing on the sepiolite. Sepiolite has also been found as thicker scabs, golden brown colored, filling small cracks.

Leafy sepiolite. Carlés North. FOV 3 cm.

Serpentine

Serpentine is found as masses of varied colors, from almost white to dark green, and pale greenish to yellow green. Given the similarity between the minerals of this group, we have not been able to identify accurately each find, although it is probable that lizardite, antigorite and clinochrysotile all occur, single or mixed.

Chrysocolla

Chrysocolla was quite common in the supergene alteration zone, forming veins and botryoidal crusts covering surfaces of several centimeters. It has a very vivid blue color, especially on fracture surfaces. The outer surfaces have a duller appearance and are less bright. It appears associated with iron oxides and relict chalcopyrite.

Chrysocolla. Carlés North FOV 3 cm.

Chapmanite $\text{Fe}^{3+}_2\text{Sb}^{3+}(\text{SiO}_4)_2(\text{OH})$

This mineral was relatively abundant in the marbles with hydrothermal altered mineralization in Carlés North. It appears as compact masses of yellowish green color. It has a clay-like appearance and fills veins several millimeters thick. It also appeared as individual spherules, extremely small,

associated with small crystals of aragonite, or forming tapestries over tiny calcite crystals. It is sometimes found associated with arsenopyrite microcrystals. Chapmanite is a fairly rare mineral. In Spain it was only previously found in the gold mine of El Valle-Boinás in Belmonte (Asturias), but in very small quantities (Mesa *et al.*, 2002).

Chapmanite on calcite. Carlés North. FOV 2,5 cm. Below, SEM photo of chapmanite on aragonite.

Orthoclase KAlSi_3O_8

Crystals of this mineral, orange colored, and in sizes up to 4 centimeters have been found. Usually it appears as single crystals formed by the combination of {001}, {010}, {110} and {10 $\bar{1}$ }, associated with quartz, actinolite, diopside-hedenbergite, arsenopyrite and löllingite within the skarn vugs, filled up in the last stage by crystalline calcite.

Scapolite $(\text{Na,Ca})_4(\text{Al,Si})_4\text{O}_8(\text{Cl,CO}_3)_4$

The presence of scapolite was indicated in small quantities at the outer limit of skarn in Carlés East. In analyses conducted by Martin Izard *et al.*, (2000) the marialite component narrowly dominates. It has been found as compact masses formed by divergent crystal aggregates. In the vugs appearing in the skarn, scapolite is rare. When it does appear, it forms bacillary or prismatic crystals up to two centimeters in length, translucent and white.

In the outcrops located along the road, before the Carlés mine became an open pit, vugs with crystals of greenish scapolite, due to the presence of inclusions of amphibole, where found. Some of the scapolite crystals from these vugs were wholly or partly transformed into plagioclase (oligoclase).

Orthoclase crystals with diopside-hedenbergite. Carlés North. Crystal height, 1.5 cm.

Scapolite crystals, green due to amphibole inclusions, with plagioclase after scapolite (pink) and garnet. This specimen, obtained in 1989, is from Carlés East. FOV 3 cm.

Plagioclase (oligoclase) $(\text{Na,Ca})[\text{Al}(\text{Si,Al})\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8]$

In the skarn, plagioclase is relatively common, and appears generally within the range of composition of oligoclase with albite being the dominant molecule (Arcos *et al.*, 1996). It also appears as small tabular crystals over garnet, with white orange to very light brown color, translucent, inside vugs filled later with crystalline calcite in Carlés North.

In the outcrops where the Carlés East workings would later be, plagioclase was found as well formed, translucent and pinkish white crystals, inside skarn cavities, on garnet crystals. As in the other cases, these cavities were completely filled by crystalline calcite. Plagioclase as partial or total pseudomorphs after scapolite has also been found in this area within vugs with the walls covered with garnet crystals. The pseudomorphs are composed of compact plagioclase or else an ordered aggregate of parallel microcrystals of this mineral, in both cases opaque and orange colored. Along with it epidote sometimes appears, which is also part of the pseudomorphs. This type of pseudomorphism seems to be relatively common, as remarkable specimens have been found at several localities, such as Griffith, Ontario (Canada), Osthagan and Nyseter in Groua, Hadeland (Norway) and in the Mary Kathleen area in Queensland (Australia).

Orthoclase crystals, 1.5 cm tall. Carlés East area.

Plagioclase after scapolite, with epidote. Carlés East. FOV 1,5 cm.

Other minerals

In the Carlés skarn there are, as quantitatively important microscopic inclusions in the sulfides, native bismuth and many rare sulfides, viewable only using reflected light microscopy. Native bismuth appears associated with chalcopyrite in mineralized veins in the exoskarn (Arcos *et al.*, 1996). It is also found as inclusions of tenths of a millimeter in arsenopyrite. The association of native bismuth with native gold is quite common. Sometimes, it is partially replaced by bismutite associated with arsenopyrite (Loredo and García Iglesias, 1988).

The antimonial variety, known as horobetsuite, appears associated with antimony-poor native bismuth and wittichenite as inclusions in chalcopyrite (Paniagua, 1998). In addition, chalcocite and covellite appear with it as alteration products of chalcopyrite (Rua Figueroa *et al.*, 1987). Wittichenite appears in significant quantities associated with chalcopyrite and with other copper and bismuth minerals in mineralized veins in the exoskarn area (Arcos *et al.*, 1996; Martin Izard *et al.*, 2000.). Hessite appears along with electrum, wittichenite, stützite, petzite, and as inclusions 50 microns in size, in bornite.

Coloradoite can be found as traces in the skarn of the gold deposit of Carlés accompanied by calaverite, petzite and other sulfides as inclusions in sphalerite (Paniagua, 1998). Other minerals such as tetradymite, joseite, joseite-B, stromeyerite, stannite, stannoidite, famatinite, pligionite, gustavite and mawsonite can be found in this locality as microscopic inclusions in bornite (Paniagua, 1998). Vulcanite is accompanied by electrum, hessite, wittichenite and other rare sulfides, appearing as inclusions in bornite and chalcopyrite (Paniagua, 1998. Martín Izard *et al.*, 2000). "Wehrlite", which is a mixture of hessite and pilsenite, has been reported as inclusions in bornite (Paniagua, 1998) as well as cubanite (García Loredó and Iglesias, 1988). The presence of tsumoite, although doubtful, has been reported accompanying other rare minerals as inclusions in chalcopyrite and bornite in the Carlés East gold deposit. Also dubious is the reported presence of rickardite (which could be wehrlite, a mixture between hessite and pilsenite) associated with chalcopyrite, wittichenite and other sulfides in the Carlés East mine (Martín Izard *et al.*, 2000). At the petrographic level, ilmenite appears in the granitoids that generated the skarn. Ilmenite is more abundant than magnetite, which can even be completely absent. This phenomenon, which indicates that the rocks were formed under reducing conditions, is important since the prevalence of ilmenite over magnetite is geochemically favorable for the formation gold bearing skarns (Martín Izard *et al.*, 2000).

References

- Arcos, D., Soler, A. y Delgado, J. (1996). Fluid evolution in the Cu-Au deposit related to the Carlés granodiorite (Asturias). *European Journal of Mineralogy*, 8, 975-985.
- Calvo, M. (2009). *Minerales y Minas de España. Vol. IV, Óxidos e Hidróxidos*. Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Minas de Madrid - Fundación Gómez Pardo. 752 pp.
- Calvo, M. (2012). *Minerales y Minas de España. Vol. V, Carbonatos y Nitratos*. Boratos. Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Minas de Madrid - Fundación Gómez Pardo. 711 pp.
- Calvo, M. (2014). *Minerales y Minas de España. Vol. VI, Sulfatos (seleniados, telurados), cromatos, molibdatos y wolframatos*. Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Minas de Madrid - Fundación Gómez Pardo. 653 pp.
- Fernández, C.J. y Blanco, M. (1992). El skarn de Cu-As de Carles (Asturias). III Congreso Geológico de España y VIII Congreso Latinoamericano de Geología, Vol. 3, 363-367.
- García de Figuerola, L.C. y de la Peña, F. (1964). El afloramiento cuarzo-diorítico de Carlés (Asturias) y la prospección geoquímica de cobre en el mismo. *Boletín de la Real Sociedad Española de Historia Natural (Geología)*, 62, 91-106.
- González, T. (1832). *Registro y Relación General de Minas de la Corona de Castilla*. Miguel de Burgos, Madrid. Vol. 1, pag. 471.
- Hergén, C. (1801). Conclusión de los materiales para la geografía mineralógica de España y de sus posesiones en América. *Anales de Ciencias Naturales*, 3, 101-111.
- Loredó, J. y García, J. (1988). El yacimiento aurífero de Carlés (Asturias). *Boletín de la Sociedad Española de Mineralogía*, 11, 47-53.
- Martín Izard, A., Paniagua, A., García, J., Fuertes, M., Boixet, L., Maldonado, C. y Varela, A. (2000). The Carlés copper-gold-molybdenum skarn (Asturias, Spain): geometry, mineral associations and metasomatic evolution. *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, 71, 153-175.
- Mesa, M., Calvo, M. y Viñals, J. (2002). El Valle-Boinás. Un proyecto moderno con minerales de excepción. *Bocamina* (9), 38-85.
- Noble, A.C., Wheeler, A. y Williams, W.C. (2012). Technical Report for the El Valle/Boinás-Carlés Gold Deposits: Updated Reserve Estimate and Mine Plan. Informe para Orvana Minerals Corp. 261 págs.
- Paillette, A. (1852). Recherches sur l'histoire et sur les conditions de gisement des mines d'or dans le nord de l'Espagne. *Bulletin de la Société Géologique de France*, 2sr, 9, 482-510. Traducido como Paillette, A. (1853). Investigaciones sobre la historia y condiciones de yacimiento de las minas de oro en el Norte de España. *Revista Minera*, 4, 450-457; 479-483.
- Paniagua, A. (1998). Ore mineralogy and thermodynamic evolution of the Carlés gold-bearing skarn. En: *Gold exploration and mining in NW Spain* (Arias, A., Martín-Izard, A. y Paniagua, A. Eds). Oviedo. 106-111.
- Perea, A. y Sánchez, F.J. (1995). *Arqueología del oro Astur*. Orfebrería y Minería. Caja de Asturias, Oviedo. 116 págs.
- Rúa Figuerola, A., Llavona, M., Loredó, J., García Iglesias, J. (1987). Fluid inclusions in quartz from a gold-mineralized granodioritic intrusion at Carlés, Asturias, Spain. *Chemical Geology*, 61, 217-224.
- Schulz, (1858). *Descripción Geológica de la Provincia de Oviedo*. Imprenta y Librería de D. José Gonzalez, Madrid. Pág. 40.
- Toreno, Conde de (1785). *Discursos Pronunciados en la Real Sociedad de Oviedo en los años de 1781 y 1783*. Madrid, Joachin Ibarra. 100 págs.
- Villa, A. y Fanjul, A. (2006). Avance al estudio arqueológico de las labores auríferas de época romana de Carlés (Asturias, España). *Actas del 3º Simposio sobre Mineración y Metalurgia Históricas no Sudoeste Europeu*. SEDPGYM, Lisboa, junio 2005. 153-167.
- Wheeler, A., Dowdell, B. y Noble, A.C. (2010). Technical Report on the Boinás and Carlés Gold Mines. Informe para Orvana Minerals Corp. 196 págs.
- Zambonini, F. (1919). Il Tufo pipernoide della Campania e suoi minerali. *Memoriper Servire alla Descrizione della Carta Geologica d'Italia*, 7, 130 págs.

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